

Relationships between Permissible Deformations on Elasto-plastic Seismic Responses and Deformations under Static Seismic Load of Single Layer Lattice Domes with Various Natural Period Ratios and Mass Ratios

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Abstract

Previous studies have investigated the evaluation of permissible deformations under seismic waves for single layer lattice domes using elasto-plastic response analysis. This paper attempts to evaluate the permissible deformation of a single layer lattice domes with various natural period ratios R_T and mass ratios R_M of the roof to the substructure, which have not been sufficiently investigated, when the domes have the geometrical initial imperfection. In addition, the relationships between the permissible deformations obtained from dynamic elasto-plastic response analyses and the results obtained from simpler analysis methods are examined. The analysis models are rigidly jointed single layer lattice domes with substructure to support the dome. The dome span is 60m, the half open angle of the domes is 30 degrees. Methods of analyses are a natural vibration analysis, a dynamic response analysis and a static buckling analysis which takes the geometrical and material nonlinearities into account.

Keywords: Single layer lattice dome, Natural period ratio, Mass ratio, elasto-plastic seismic response analysis, static seismic load, evaluation of permissible deformation

1. Introduction

The single layer lattice structures are also used for evacuation facility and disaster prevention base in a time of disaster such as an earthquake or a typhoon. Therefore, it is hoped that the elasto-plastic seismic response behavior of these structures is clarified and controlled. Several studies (Kato *et al.* [1], Ishikawa *et al.* [2], Kumagai *et al.* [3]-[7] etc.) have been made on the response behavior of the single layer lattice structures subjected to earthquake motions. However, there are no previous studies with dealing about the evaluation of permissible plastic deformation of the spatial structures subjected to earthquake motions except for our study (Kumagai *et al.* [5]-[7]). Previous studies have investigated the evaluation of permissible deformations under seismic waves for single layer lattice domes using elasto-plastic response analysis. From the above, this paper attempts to evaluate the permissible deformation of a single layer lattice domes with various natural period ratios R_T and mass ratios R_M of the roof to the substructure, which have not been sufficiently investigated, when the domes have the geometrical initial imperfection. In addition, the relationships between the permissible deformations obtained from dynamic elasto-plastic response analyses and the results obtained from simpler analysis methods are examined. The evaluation method of permissible deformations is almost the same as in the reference (Kumagai *et al.* [7]). Specifically, the permissible deformations are evaluated by plastic rotation angles when the slope of the plastic rotation angle with respect to the input acceleration exceeds from the origin of the plastic rotation angle at 90% of the input acceleration at which the dome collapses by focusing attention on the nodal rotations and the rotational angles at center of members.

2. Outlines of numerical analysis for single layer lattice domes

2.1. Analysis models

The analysis models are rigidly jointed single layer lattice domes with supporting substructure to support the dome shown in Fig.1. The dome span is 60m, the half open angle of the domes θ is 30 degrees. The joints between the tension ring of dome roof and the top of column of the supporting substructure are pin joints. For the boundary condition, the bases of columns are pin supported. The shapes of geometric initial imperfection are similar shapes to eigenmodes with large effective mass of lattice domes without geometric initial imperfection. The maximum amplitudes of the imperfection are set for $0.2 \times t_{eq}$. Where t_{eq} is the equivalent shell thickness evaluated by Eq.(1).

$$t_{eq} = 2\sqrt{3}i \quad (1)$$

Where i is the radius of gyration of area of members of dome roof.

Figure 1: Analysis model and name analysis models (Single layer lattice dome)

Table 1 shows the member properties and shell-like factors ζ_0 . The members of the dome roof are designed so that the safety factors of combined stresses of the members under the dead load of the dome will be uniform by the allowable stress design with safety factor $\nu = 2.5$. The names of analysis models are defined as shown in Fig.1. The ratios of mass of substructure to that of roof structure (mass ratio) R_M are varied by multiplying the mass of the supporting substructure by 1, 10 and 20. R_M are set to 1.2, 3.1 and 5.3. The ratios R_T of the natural period of equivalent single mass system T_{eq} to the predominant natural period of dome structure with antisymmetrical 1 wave T_R are set to 0.8, 1.0 and 1.2. R_T is held constant at 0.8 when varying R_M . R_M is held constant at 1.2 when varying R_T . The stress-strain relationship is assumed to be a bi-linear type for dome roof members and a linear type for the other members. The intermediate nodes are set to the members of the dome roof in order to the member buckling occurring smoothly. The mass which corresponds to the dead load of the dome is given to each node. The dead load is assumed to be 1.18 kN/m^2 for the dome roof and 0.98 kN/m^2 for the supporting substructure in consideration of the structural material weight and finishing material weight, etc.

Table1: Member properties and shell-like factors

The half open angle of the dome θ (deg.)	30			
	Dome (on Ridge)	Tension ring	Substructure (column)	Substructure (beam)
Safety factor ν	2.5	5.0	1.0	
Tube diameter D (cm)	16.52	60.96	91.44	60.96
Tube thickness t (cm)	0.40~0.65	1.27	1.60	1.27
Slenderness ratio λ	91.7~93.1	21.2	18.9	21.2
Shell-like factor ζ_0	4.24			
Young's modulus E (N/mm ²)	2.06×10 ⁵			
Modulus of strain hardening E_t (N/mm ²)	2.06×10 ³			
Yield stress σ_y (N/mm ²)	294			

Fig.2 shows the shapes of natural vibrational modes adopted as geometric initial imperfection. The natural periods and effective mass ratios for horizontal x direction are shown in figures. It is known from the previous study (Kumagai *et al.*[5] and [8]) that the collapse accelerations of a single-layer lattice dome are greatly reduced when the shapes of predominant modes with shorter wavelengths are adopted as initial imperfection. In this study, the modes adopted for the initial imperfection are selected according to this result. The shapes of initial imperfection are similar to the shape of the dome roof in these modes. The tension ring and substructure are shaped without imperfections.

Figure 2: Shapes of natural vibrational modes adopted as geometric initial imperfection

2.2. Numerical analysis methods

Methods of analyses are a natural vibration analysis, a dynamic response analysis and a static buckling analysis which takes the geometrical and material nonlinearities into account. These analyses are performed by in-house programs. A numerical integration scheme is the Newmark $\beta = 1/4$ method. The time increment Δt is 0.005s. Rayleigh damping is applied to the dome damping. The dead load P_S are applied quasi-statically by using a critical damping factor $h = 1.00$ at the time t ranging from 0.0 to 0.5s, and then the dynamic load P_D is added by using a damped vibration ($h_1, h_2 = 0.02$) at $t = 2.0s$. Where h_1 and h_2 are the damping factors of 1st and 2nd modes respectively. The incremental arc-length method is used to find the equilibrium path of the solution in static analysis.

2.3. Input earthquake ground motions

The input directions of seismic waves are x direction as shown in Fig.1. The acceleration response spectra of input earthquake motions used for the dynamic response analyses are shown in Fig.3. The input earthquake motions are El Centro NS, Taft EW and random waves. El Centro NS and Taft EW are the simulated earthquake motions with phase characteristics of El Centro NS (1940) and Taft EW (1952) respectively. The characteristic of response spectrum for horizontal component is based on notification 1461 (Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism of Japan). In the following, simulated earthquake motions with respective phase characteristics of observed seismic waves will be referred to as “Simulated El Centro NS”, “Simulated Taft EW” and “Simulated Random”. The maximum accelerations of input earthquake motions for each direction are shown in Table 2. The magnitude of input earthquake motion is defined by the earthquake motion intensity λ_E . $\lambda_E = 1.0$ represents the level of damage limit by notification 1461. $\lambda_E = 5.0$ represents the level of safety limit. The input accelerations are the horizontal earthquake ground motions. The maximum duration of input seismic waves are 15s.

Figure 3: Acceleration response spectra of input earthquake motions ($h = 2\%$)

Table2: Maximum accelerations of input earthquake motions ($\lambda_E = 1.0$)

Input earthquake motion	Horizontal component
Simulated El Centro NS	103.4
Simulated Taft EW	121.7
Simulated Random	121.5

3. Definitions for rotational angles of single layer lattice domes

In determining the collapse accelerations of single layer lattice domes, the maximum plastic rotation angle θ_{pl}^{max} is defined. The definitions for the nodal rotation angles and rotational angles at center of member are shown in Fig.4. Fig.5 shows the definitions for plastic rotation angles θ_{pl} . The plastic rotation angles are obtained by skeleton curve as shown in figure. The maximum plastic rotation angle θ_{pl}^{max} is taken as the maximum value of all members of dome roof. Where the collapse seismic intensity λ_{Ecr} is defined as the seismic intensity λ_E when the maximum plastic rotation angle of the roof structural member reaches 0.08 rad when λ_E is gradually increased (Kumagai *et al.*[7]).

Figure 4: Definitions for rotational angles

Figure 5: Definitions for plastic rotation angles

4. Permissible deformation of single layer lattice domes in dynamic elasto-plastic response analysis

4.1. Elasto-plastic seismic response behavior of single layer lattice domes

Fig.6 shows the relationships between maximum values of rotation angles θ^{max} for all members of domes and the earthquake motion intensity λ_E for models with various R_M and R_T at the input of Simulated El Centro NS. After the maximum values of rotation angles increase with nearly linear relation with the increase in the λ_E , the values of rotation angles increase rapidly with nonlinear relation. The nodal rotation angles are larger than the rotational angle at center of member in both the models with imperfections and those without imperfections. This indicates that the subject dome tends to exhibit total buckling. The rotation angles increase with the increase in the R_M and the decrease in the R_T , and are larger in the models with imperfections than those without imperfections. From the above, in this paper, the nodal rotation angles are adopted to determine λ_{Ecr} .

Figure 6: Relationships between maximum values of rotation angles θ^{max} for all members of domes and the earthquake motion intensity λ_E (Simulated El Centro NS)

4.2. Evaluation of average values of plastic rotation angles

The evaluation method of permissible deformations is almost the same as in the reference (Kumagai *et al.* [7]). In this chapter, we introduce the product of the sum of the plastic rotation angles of the members of dome roof $\Sigma\theta_{pl}$ and the plasticity ratio r_{pl}^{mem} ($=N_{pl}^{mem} / N_R^{mem}$) which is an indicator for representing the ratio of the number of plasticized members N_{pl}^{mem} to the number of roof members excluding the tension ring N_R^{mem} . With the introduction of this indicator, the permissible deformation will be analyzed from the viewpoint of the average value of the plastic rotation angles of the plasticized members in the all members of dome $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$. Keeping the rate of increase of $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ relative to $(\lambda - \lambda_y) / (\lambda_{cr} - \lambda_y)$ smaller than the slope (the rate of increase in $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$) for the secant line at 0.9 of $(\lambda - \lambda_y) / (\lambda_{cr} - \lambda_y)$ (hereinafter called “permissible slope S^{per} ”) are considered. It was considered that the structural

instability phenomenon will not occur immediately in the dome if increase rate of $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ can be suppressed to S^{per} or less. Based on this consideration, the point where the permissible slope S^{per} and the rate of increase of $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ relative to $(\lambda - \lambda_y) / (\lambda_{cr} - \lambda_y)$ intersect is defined as the permissible average plastic rotation angle $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ (Kumagai *et al.*[7]). However, the method in the study (Kumagai *et al.*[7]) does not include the structural characteristics of the structure up to the onset of initial yielding, and may not have properly evaluated the permissible deformation in a model with a small margin between initial yielding and collapse. Therefore, in this paper, in order to take into account the structural characteristics of the structure up to the onset of initial yielding, the permissible deformation is evaluated not as $(\lambda - \lambda_y) / (\lambda_{cr} - \lambda_y)$ in the study (Kumagai *et al.*[7]) but as $\lambda_E / \lambda_{Ecr}$ as shown in the Fig.7.

Figure 7: Evaluation of permissible deformation

Fig.8 shows the relationships between the seismic intensity $\lambda_E / \lambda_{Ecr}$ and the average value of the plastic rotation angles $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ at the input of Simulated El Centro NS. In the figure, the results of the power approximation expressed as $y = ax^b + c$ are also shown. The purpose of this approximation is to smooth out the variation that occurs in the slope described above in the numerical analysis results. In the figure, only the rotation angles with large $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ to be evaluated are shown. The blue points in the figure show $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$. $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ show small values at 0.9 with the increase in the R_T and the decrease in the R_M in both the models with imperfections and those without imperfections and the secant lines at 0.9 of $\lambda_E / \lambda_{Ecr}$ become larger. Similarly, $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ show small values with the increase in the R_T and the decrease in the R_M . The permissible deformations are evaluated as the points at which $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ begins to increase with respect to an increase in λ_E .

Figure 8: Relationships between seismic intensity $\lambda_E / \lambda_{Ecr}$ and average value of plastic rotation angles $\Sigma\theta_{pl} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ (Simulated El Centro NS)

4.3. Permissible deformation corresponding to permissible average plastic rotation angle

In this section, $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ and corresponding response quantities obtained from Section 4.2. are considered. Here, we introduce the factor product FP that expresses the dome under consideration. FP is the shell-like factor $\zeta_0 \times (1 / \text{safety factor } \nu) \times$ the response amplification factor F_V' \times knockdown factor for initial imperfection $\alpha_{imp} \times$ maximum effective mass ratio M_e/M_{eq} . Table 3 shows factors and factor products to be considered of each model. Where λ_0 is the typical member slenderness ratio and ψ_0 is the half open angle of member. The response amplification factor F_V' is estimated from the evaluation formulae for the response amplification factors considering the mass ratio in Takeuchi and Kumagai *et al.* [9] (Eqs. (2), (3)).

$$F_V' \begin{cases} 3C_V\theta & (0 < R_T \leq 5/16) \\ (\sqrt{5/R_T} - 1) C_V\theta. & (5/16 < R_T \leq 5) \\ 0 & (5 < R_T) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$F_V' = \sqrt{F_V^2 + \frac{1}{(1 - R_T^2)^2 + (1/R_M)}} \quad (3)$$

Where $C_V = 1.85$, the unit of half open angle θ is rad.

Table3: Factors and factor products to be considered of each model

θ	R_T	R_M	imp	ζ_0	ν	F_V'	α_{imp}	M_e/M_{eq}	FP
30	0.8	1.2	p	4.24	2.5	1.775	1.0	0.439	1.321
			62				0.562	0.135	0.726
		3.1	p			2.079	1.0	0.253	0.892
			40				0.562	0.163	1.026
		5.3	p			2.292	1.0	0.283	1.098
			38				0.562	0.164	1.133
	1.0	1.2	p	1.623	1.0	0.862	2.379		
			39		0.562	0.848	4.164		
	1.2	1.2	p	1.411	1.0	0.954	2.287		
			38		0.562	0.953	4.067		

Fig.9 shows the relationships between permissible deformations and FP . The permissible maximum vertical responses are obtained as the maximum vertical response of all roof nodes from the time history response when the seismic intensity λ_E (permissible seismic intensity λ_E^{per}) corresponding to $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$. The vertical axis in Fig.9 (b) is divided by the dome span $L (= 6000\text{cm})$. Although there is variation, $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{mem}$ tend to decrease as FP increase. The permissible maximum vertical response decreases with the increase in the R_T . In particular, $\Sigma\theta_{pl}^{per} \cdot r_{pl}^{me}$ is very small for models with $R_T=1.2$. The minimum value of D_{max}^{per} / L is about 1/500 and that of A_{max}^{per} is about 2000cm/s² in both the models with imperfections and those without imperfections.

Figure 9: Relationships between permissible deformations and FP

5. Relationships between permissible deformations and deformations in dynamic elastic analysis or static analysis

In the previous chapter, the permissible deformations were evaluated by dynamic elasto-plastic response analysis. In this chapter, the correspondences with the results of dynamic elastic analysis and static analysis are discussed in consideration of its use at the design stage.

5.1. Relationships between permissible deformations and deformations in dynamic elastic analysis

Dynamic elastic analysis is performed for permissible seismic intensity λ_E^{per} at the input of Simulated El Centro NS. Fig.10 shows a comparison of the maximum vertical responses of the dynamic elastic and dynamic elasto-plastic analyses. Vertical displacements in the elasto-plastic analysis tend to be larger than that in the elastic analysis. On the other hand, vertical accelerations in the elastic analyses are larger than that in the elasto-plastic analysis. The maximum vertical responses increase with the increase in the R_M and the decrease in the R_T for both dynamic elasto-plastic and elastic analyses. The difference in response values between dynamic elasto-plastic and elastic analyses is not so large for the maximum vertical displacement, but is large for $R_M=3.1$ and 5.3 for the maximum vertical acceleration.

Figure 10: Comparisons of maximum vertical responses of dynamic elastic and dynamic elasto-plastic analyses (Simulated El Centro NS)

5.2. Relationships between permissible deformations and deformations in static analysis

Static elastic or elasto-plastic buckling analysis is performed for static seismic loads determined by the acceleration distribution evaluation equations proposed in Takeuchi and Kumagai *et al.* [9]. In this chapter, only perfect shapes are considered. The loads are the static seismic loads for dead loads and horizontal seismic motions. The static seismic loads are calculated as the product of the response acceleration obtained from the acceleration distribution evaluation equations $A_{HorV(x,y)}$ (Eqs.(4) and (5)) and the mass at each node of the roof surface.

$$A_{H(x,y)} = A_{eq} \left\{ 1 + (F'_H - 1) \cos \frac{\pi \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{L} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$A_{V(x,y)} = A_{eq} F'_V \frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}} \sin \frac{2\pi \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{L} \quad (5)$$

Where F'_H and F'_V are the response amplification factors in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively, taking into account the resonance associated with the increase in the mass ratio R_M . A_{eq} is the response acceleration of the one mass model, and x and y are the coordinates of the horizontal plane. F'_H and F'_V are obtained from Eqs. (2), (3) described in Section 4.3. and (6), (7).

$$F'_H = \sqrt{F_H^2 + \frac{1}{(1 - R_T^2)^2 + (1/R_M)^\theta}} \quad (6)$$

$$F_H = \sqrt{5/4R_T} \quad (7)$$

Fig.11 shows the correspondences between the permissible deformations obtained from the dynamic analysis and the results of the static analysis. The static analysis results are the displacements and accelerations corresponding to the permissible seismic intensity λ_E^{per} of the relationship between the vertical load of the static seismic load and the vertical displacement at node D. The vertical accelerations are the evaluated values of the acceleration distribution corresponding to λ_E^{per} . The vertical acceleration is the evaluated value of acceleration distribution corresponding to λ_E^{per} . The permissible values in dynamic elasto-plastic analysis compared to static analysis are 0.6~3 times for permissible vertical displacement and 0.5~2 times for permissible vertical acceleration.

Figure 11: Relationship between permissible response for static and dynamic analysis

6. Conclusions

Summary of results obtained may be as follows.

- 1) The minimum allowable vertical responses in the dynamic elasto-plastic response analysis of the domes in this study is approximately $1/500$ for the permissible maximum vertical displacement D_{max}^{per} / L and 2000cm/s^2 for the permissible maximum vertical accelerations A_{max}^{per} , regardless of whether or not geometric initial imperfections are taken into consideration.
- 2) Comparing dynamic elasto-plastic analysis with elastic analysis, we find that vertical displacements in the elasto-plastic analysis tend to be larger than that in the elastic analysis. On the other hand, vertical accelerations in the elastic analyses are larger than that in the elasto-plastic analysis. The maximum vertical responses increase with the increase in the R_M and the decrease in the R_T for both dynamic elasto-plastic and elastic analyses.
- 3) The permissible values in dynamic elasto-plastic analysis compared to static analysis are 0.6~3 times for permissible vertical displacement and 0.5~2 times for permissible vertical acceleration.

References

- [1] Kato S., Ueki T. and Mukaiyama Y., Study of dynamic collapse of single layer reticular domes subjected to earthquake motion and the estimation of statically equivalent seismic forces, *International Journal of Space Structures*, 1997; **12**(3–4); 191–203.
- [2] Ishikawa K. and Kato S., Elasto-plastic dynamic buckling analysis of reticular domes subjected to earthquake motion, *International Journal of Space Structures*, 1997; **12**(3–4); 205–215.
- [3] Kumagai T. and Ogawa T., Dynamic buckling behavior of single layer lattice domes under horizontal single pulse waves, *Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering (Transaction of AIJ)*, 2004; **585**; 115–122 (in Japanese).
- [4] Kumagai T., Ogawa T., Takeuchi T. and Sato E., A prediction method of dynamic collapse behavior of single-layer latticed domes subjected to horizontal earthquake motions, *Proceedings of IASS 2007*, 2007; 215–216.
- [5] Kumagai T., Yasuda M. and Ogawa T., Effects of geometric initial imperfection on dynamic collapse behavior of single layer lattice domes subjected to horizontal earthquake motions, *Proceedings of the IASS Symposium 2015*, 2015; 1–11.
- [6] Kumagai T., Yamana D. and Ogawa T., Elasto-plastic seismic response behavior and evaluation of allowable deformation of single layer lattice domes with geometric initial imperfection, in *Spatial Structures in the 21st Century: Proceedings of the IASS Annual Symposium 2016*, Tokyo, Japan, 2016.
- [7] T. Kumagai and T. Ogawa, “Elasto-plastic Seismic Response Behavior and Evaluation of Permissible Deformation of Single Layer Lattice Domes Designed under Various Loads,” *Proc. of the IASS Ann. Symp. 2020/2021 and 7th int’l Conf. on Spatial struc.*, pp.1-11(USB flash drive), 2021.
- [8] Yasuda M., Yamana D., Kumagai T., Ogawa T., Seismic collapse behavior for single layer lattice domes with various geometric initial imperfections, *Summaries of Technical Papers of Annual Meeting, Architectural Institute of Japan*, 2017, B-1; 853-854 (in Japanese)
- [9] Takeuchi T., Kumagai T., Shirabe H. and Ogawa T., Seismic response evaluation of lattice shell roofs supported by multistory structures, *Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering, Architectural Institute of Japan*, 2007; 619; 97-104 (in Japanese.)